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Executive summary

Evaluating exit programmes/interventions is a challenging endeavor. The current document presents an evaluation framework for the assessment of these interventions/programmes. The evaluation framework considers a set of attributes that can be evaluated, based on the previous literature review (cf. Deliverable 3.1). Attributes such as programme design, programmes' contact approach and type of participation are initially defined. Then, interview questions and questionnaire items are developed for each attribute considered. Finally, a strategy for the implementation of the evaluation is designed considering different levels of achievement.

1. Introduction

The present report presents a common framework for the evaluation of exit programmes that will be implemented for the assessment of mapped existing exit intervention. The framework was developed considering the previous literature review on evaluation methods presented in deliverable 3.1. Moreover, feasibility played a key part in the design of the evaluation framework, since we need to both develop a complete framework while remaining capable of implementing the peer review of existing exit interventions. Therefore, the evaluation framework encompasses an online questionnaire and a possible two-interviews stage that will be used to gather information on the programmes. The report proceeds as follows: section 2 presents the framework development, including: the attributes chosen for the evaluation of exit programmes (sub-section 2.1); the online questionnaire (sub-section 2.2); the interview questions (sub-section 2.3) with both questions for programme managers/head of implementation team and other actors/programme stakeholders (sub-section 2.4); finishing with the implementation of the evaluation framework. Section 3 presents the conclusions of the report.

2. Framework development

2.1. Evaluation attributes

Before developing the framework, we started with the identification of evaluation dimensions (attributes) that will guide the development of the questionnaire and interviews. Considering the information we want to collect from different programmes, the attributes shown in Table 1 were identified.

Table 1- Evaluation dimensions and reasoning for inclusion

Attribute/dimension that is being evaluated	Reasoning
Type of Intervention	Considering that Exit programmes can encompass different strategies, we aim at understanding how the programme is labelled.
Actor	To know if the programme is being implemented by a governmental body, NGO, or if it results from a public-private partnership.
Exit Programme design and conceptualisation	A good programme design, establishing a set of coherent and clear goals and a course of action is essential to ensure its structural quality. The theoretical basis of the programme will provide some guarantee of achieving results and linking results to programme actions.
Team	Programmes are implemented by people. Therefore, it is important to know how staff is selected and initially trained, who is implementing the programme and how different members' skills are combined in the case of multidisciplinary teams.
Contact approach	We want to assess the programmes' contact approach, that is, if they have

	a proactive communication strategy to reach potential participants or even a more coercive approach or if they follow a more passive approach, relying on potential participants initiative to reach the existing programme. The contact approach can have an impact on participants motivation and programme success.
Type of participation	It is important to know if the programme has a voluntary or mandatory participation. Concerns exit about mandatory participation (cf. Barkindo & Bryans, 2016)
Ideology	Considering the differences between deradicalisation and disengagement (cf. WayOut's deliverable 2.1), we want to explore if the programme encompasses an ideological component, (i.e., if it has deradicalisation goals or if it aims mainly at disengage individuals).
Duration	In order to understand how long the programme takes from start to finish and which impact this has on participants turnover and project success.
Programme characteristics	Our aim is to know if the programme is implemented on an individual or group level.
Multi-agency approach / collaboration	We want to know how the organisation implementing the programme collaborates with other agents that are relevant for the programme implementation.
Risk and needs assessment	How the programme incorporates risk and needs assessment of participants (inmates/probationers). What kind of instruments are being used and how frequently is the assessment done.
Monitorisation / Follow-up / Aftercare	We want to know if the programmes have post-intervention monitorisation or follow-up procedures and how long they keep providing aftercare for participants.
Transparency	Refers to information sharing about the programme with the media or with key actors.
Assessment (Overall)	Regarding programmes assessment, we are interested in knowing how interventions' success is measured, why the intervention is considered effective/ineffective, what the evaluation of the programmes lead to and if the cost-effectiveness of the intervention is taken into consideration.
(Assessment) Mechanism	
Assessment (Policy)	
(Assessment) Economic	
Fine-tuning	To understand if the programme is being fine-tuned as a result of evaluation or theoretical updates.
Evaluation reports	To know if the programme has produced evaluation reports and if those reports are available.

Therefore, the identification of attributes is therefore useful in order to guide the construction of the online questionnaire and interviews for the assessment of exit interventions. The following

sub-section details the construction of the questionnaire items.

2.2. Online questionnaire

With the advantage of being less time-consuming than the interview, therefore enhancing the probability of reaching programme managers/head of implementation teams or other actors that may not be available for the interview, an online questionnaire was constructed. Items were developed considering the previously defined attributes. Most items are answered with a 7-point Likert-type response scale from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”. However, other items consider a multiple-choice answer of a time-frequency scale. The online questionnaire will represent the first data collection method to be implemented for the evaluation of the exit programmes. They target respondents with a deep understanding about the programme attributes. Table 4 presents the items.

Table 2 - Online questionnaire items

Attribute/dimension that is being evaluated	Item
Type of intervention	How do you describe your exit programme? (select as applicable): As a Taylor-made intervention As a cognitive skills programme As a psychosocial intervention As an education course As a vocational skill training As a set of creative, cultural and recreational activities Other: Does the programme considers the involvement of (select as applicable): Participant’s family and social networks Religious experts Victims Former violent extremists Influential personalities Other:
Actor	[multiple choice question] How would you describe your organisation? - Non-governmental organisation; - Company; - Governmental organisation; - Other organisation.
Exit Programme design and conceptualisation	Design of the intervention programme can be improved. Design of the programme took into consideration up-to-date scientific literature.
Team	The implementation team is comprised of skilled professionals. The implementation team is multidisciplinary.
Contact approach	A communication strategy to reach potential participants is put in place.

Type of participation	Participation in the programme is voluntary.
Ideology	The programme has a strong ideological component.
Duration	Duration of the intervention programme is appropriate.
Programme characteristics	The programme is implemented on an individual basis.
Multi-agency approach / collaboration	There is a strong collaboration between our organisation and other agencies (police, prison, community organisations, etc.).
Risk and needs assessment	Tools are used to assess participants needs. Tools are used to draw an individual intervention plan to address participants' needs. Tools are used to assess participants risk level. Tools are used to draw and individual intervention plan addressing participants risks.
Monitorisation / Follow-up / Aftercare	Post-intervention monitorisation actions are implemented. Former participants are followed-up The programme is connected to a long-term aftercare plan.
Assessment (Overall)	A clear evaluation framework is implemented to assess the programme. Participants are involved in the programme's evaluation. Stakeholders (e.g., governmental bodies; NGOs; participants' family, friends and social networks) are involved in the programme's evaluation.
Assessment (Mechanism)	Programme effectiveness mechanisms are being assessed.
Assessment (Policy)	Evaluation results are used for decisions on project funding. Evaluation results are used for decisions on project continuity.
Assessment (Economic)	Cost-effectiveness of the intervention is assessed.
Fine-tuning	The intervention programme is fine-tuned. The intervention programme is fine-tuned with inputs from the programme evaluation. The intervention programme is fine-tuned according to new theoretical developments.
Evaluation reports	Programme evaluation reports are produced and available to national authorities. Programme evaluation reports are produced and publicly available.

2.3. Interview questions

Targeted at EPs/ESs manager/head of implementation team

After combining a different set of evaluation dimensions, interview questions were developed. The first interview protocol targets Exit programmes/strategies managers/head of implementation teams. Here, we target individuals with a high degree of knowledge regarding different aspects of the programme (i.e., the attributes considered), no matter if they actually developed the programme since the programme was likely developed during a considerable period of time by a group of different individuals. Considering we are developing a framework for the evaluation of different programmes, the questions are kept broad enough so that respondents can give us their insights on the different dimensions. Moreover, following a semi-structured interview

methodology, we are providing the evaluators/interviewers questions and topics (i.e., the attributes/dimensions) that must be covered. However, we still give some discretion to the interviewer in terms of order and inclusion of other questions. The purpose of the interview is to “delve deeply into a topic and to understand thoroughly the answers provided” (Harrell & Bradley, 2018, p. 27). Since the interviews are preceded by an online questionnaire, results from the questionnaire answers will play a key role in guiding the interview script. This means that if a certain attribute needs to be deeply explored, the interviewer can flag it previously and prepare any additional questions if needed. On other hand, if questionnaires fully clarify an evaluation dimension (e.g., a “strongly agree” answer to the item “Participation in the programme is voluntary.”) perhaps the question can be skipped or used to further explore the topic (e.g., respondent answers “strongly agree to the item “Tools are used to assess participants needs.”; Interviewer wants to explore this topic and therefore asks “Is there any specific risk assessment/instrument/tool under implementation? How frequently is the assessment done?

What is done with the results of the risks assessment?”. That being said, on Table 2 we present potential interview questions, meaning that their use will be weighted according to the results from the previous stage.

Table 3 - Interview questions targeted at EPs/ESs manager/head of implementation team

Attribute/dimension that is being evaluated	Question and sub-questions
	<p>First stage - know more about the programme</p> <p>This section can start with an open question such as “How would you describe the Exit programme you are managing/implementing/working on?”</p>
Actor	Who is running the programme (organisation)? For how long? How was the programme initially funded? Which institution (governmental / non-governmental) is funding the programme?
Exit Programme design and conceptualisation	<p>What identified needs led to the creation of the programme?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Who was responsible for the programme design? - Was the programme design based on theoretical models in the field of deradicalisation?
Team	<p>What skills one needs to have to be part of the team implementing this programme? What kind of skills do you search for in potential team members?</p> <p>Who is implementing the programme (team)?</p>
Contact approach	Do you use any kind of proactive communication strategy in order to reach potential participants in the intervention programme?
Type of participation	(independently of the contact approach) To what extent is the participation in the programme voluntary?
Ideology	Does the programme have an ideological component? That is, does it target inmates/probationers’ ideology?
Duration	How long does the programme takes from start to finish?
Programme characteristics	<p>Is the programme implemented on an individual or group level?</p> <p>Do you work with participants’ families and social networks?</p>
Multi-agency approach / collaboration	How does your organisation collaborate with different agencies (e.g., law enforcement) for increasing the success of the intervention? How does your

	organisation protect participants' data when collaborating with other agencies?
Risk and needs assessment	<p>How are inmates' risks assessed at intake and during the programme?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is there any specific risk assessment/instrument/tool under implementation? - How frequently is the assessment done? - What is done with the results of the risks assessment? <p>If no risk assessment is currently being conducted, do you expect this to change in the (near) future?</p> <p>How are inmates' needs assessed at intake and during the programme?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is there any specific needs assessment/instrument/tool under implementation? - How frequently is the assessment done? - What is done with the results of the needs assessment? <p>If no needs assessment is currently being conducted, do you expect this to change in the (near) future?</p>
Monitorisation / Follow-up / Aftercare	<p>Do you apply any post-intervention/programme monitoring? If yes, when does the monitoring of participant's ends? Do you run a follow-up of the programme participants? How often?</p> <p>To what extent are other organisations involved in aftercare / are other organisations taking over after the exit programme?</p>
Transparency	<p>How do you ensure the right amount of information sharing with key actors/stakeholders (e.g., governmental bodies; NGOs; participants' family, friends and social networks)? How do you avoid the sharing of irrelevant/confidential information regarding the programme? Does the programme has a plan for crisis communication?</p>
Second stage - programme evaluation	
Assessment (Overall)	How do you measure the level of success of the programme?
Assessment (Mechanism)	Why was the intervention considered effective/ineffective? (e.g., the dynamic between the facilitator and the participants);
Assessment (Policy)	What is the impact of the evaluation on project funding and project continuity?
Assessment (Economic)	Did your organisation assess the cost-effectiveness of the programme? And if so, how has this been assessed?
Fine-tuning	Were evaluation results used to fine-tuning the programme? Is the programme reviewed according to updated scientific research?
Evaluation reports	Do you have any publicly available evaluation reports?
Closure	<p>Would you like to add something to what was previously said?</p> <p>Do you have any doubts, comments or suggestions?</p> <p>Would you recommend us another person to be involved in a similar interview? Can you bring us into contact with a programme stakeholder?</p>

Targeted at stakeholders

The first interviewees are also intended to provide the contact of a stakeholder/actor, in order to comprehend how the selection procedure and implementation of an exit programme took place. Here, a stakeholder is considered another organisation/group that has an interest or concern in the successful implementation of the programme. Moreover, the stakeholder has a strong relationship with the organisation that runs the programme, being involved in the implementation

as a partner or agency and understands programme goals and the theoretical basis of the intervention, being an active actor of the intervention programme. The potential questions developed at this stage are presented in Table 3.

Table 4 - Interview questions targeted at stakeholders

Attribute/dimension that is being evaluated	Question and sub-questions
First stage - know more about the programme	
Actor	Can you please explain what your role and the role of your organisation in the programme implementation is?
Exit Programme design and conceptualisation	To what extent are the programme's interventions adjusted to the specific needs of your country (or region) and the needs of the target group?
Team	To what extent was the implementation team qualified?
Contact approach	Are you/your organisation involved in the communication strategy to reach potential participants to the intervention programme? Are participants being reached as intended?
Ideology	To what extent was the ideological approach of the programme crucial during the selection process?
Duration	Do you consider the duration of the programme appropriate?
Risk and needs assessment	How are inmates' risks and needs assessed? Is there any specific risk assessment/instrument/tool under implementation? How frequently is the assessment done? If no risk assessment is currently being conducted, do you expect this to change in the (near) future?
Monitorisation / Follow-up	Are you aware of how post-intervention programme monitoring will occur (if there is one)? Are you aware of how participants are followed-up? Is there a plan for aftercare?
Second stage - programme evaluation	
Assessment (Overall)	To what extent is the programme achieving the intended outcomes, in the short, medium and long term? To what extent is the programme producing worthwhile results (outputs, outcomes) and/or meeting each of its objectives?
Assessment (Mechanism)	To what extent does the programme address an identified need?
Assessment (Policy)	How well does the programme align with government and agency priorities?
Assessment (Economic)	What has been the ratio of costs to benefits? Has the intervention been cost-effective (compared to alternatives)? Is the programme the best use of resources? Do the outcomes of the programme represent value for money? To what extent is the relationship between inputs and outputs timely, cost-effective and to expected standards? How did you justify the need to implement this programme, as a

	priority?
Fine-tuning	Were evaluation results used to fine-tuning the programme? Is the programme reviewed according to updated scientific research?
Evaluation reports	<p>Did the programme produce or contribute to the intended outcomes in the short, medium and long term?</p> <p>What unintended outcomes (positive and negative) were produced?</p> <p>To what extent can changes be attributed to the programme?</p> <p>What were the features of the programme and context that made a difference?</p> <p>What was the influence of other factors?</p> <p>What has been done in an innovative way?</p> <p>How satisfied are programme clients?</p>

2.4. Implementation of the evaluation framework

Regarding the implementation of the evaluation of exit programmes, the following four scenarios are considered:

- a) **Ideal evaluation of the exit programme will encompass:** Online questionnaire filled in by programme manager or member of the implementation team; an interview with programme manager/head of implementation team; an interview with a project stakeholder;
- b) **If two interviews are not possible:** Online questionnaire filled in by programme manager or member of the implementation team; an interview with programme manager/head of implementation team;
- c) **If no interview can be done:** Online questionnaire filled in by programme manager or member of the implementation team.
- d) **If initial contact refuses to fill in or share the online questionnaire:** An interview with programme manager/head of implementation team.

Additional rules apply as follows:

- In case the manager/head of implementation team is not available for the interview, a member of the implementation team can be interviewed;
- Preferably, if two data collection methods are used (i.e., questionnaire and interview), information should come from two different persons. Only if this is not possible, the same person can answer the online questionnaire and be interviewed.

In order to start the evaluation of existing exit programmes, the following steps will be taken by the partnership:

- i) **Compiling the existing exit programmes:** Partners will collect all available information about current exit programmes being implemented, with a focus on the European context, aiming at mapping all relevant programmes for the purpose of our project (cf.

- Deliverable 3.4).
- ii) **Contacting organisations:** Whether projects are run by NGO's or governmental organisations, project managers (or whenever a direct contact exists with another element of the organisation) will be contacted to reach more information about the project (e.g., if its active) and interviews with key informants will be scheduled. At this phase, a potential respondent to the online questionnaire should be identified.
 - iii) **Questionnaires:** Link to the online questionnaire will be sent to the target respondent.
 - iv) **Interviews phase I:** At this stage, interviews will be done and contacts to potential stakeholders will be made.
 - v) **Interviews phase II:** Interviews with stakeholders will be done at this stage, whenever this is possible.
 - vi) **Other data collection procedures:** If possible, additional information (such as evaluation reports) will be collected.

3. Conclusions

Based on the literature review report (D3.1) and bearing in mind the limitations related to the projects' timeframe, the current deliverable presents an evaluation framework for exit interventions. It starts by setting the attributes that will be used for the evaluation of the mapped exit programmes. Moreover, it draws an evaluation strategy and the needed tools (i.e., interviews and questionnaire) for its implementation. Therefore, this deliverable will allow the development of the evaluation framework user manual (D3.3), creating the groundwork to the interviews phase.

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